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CONTRIBUTION OF CENTRAL REGULATORS OF THE IMMUNE RESPONSE TO THE DEVELOPMENT OF THYROID DISEASES

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Annotation. *The specific relationship between the endocrine and immune systems is represented by a numerous number of factors and mechanisms that form the structure and ensure the function of each of the two systems. For example, immunocompetent cells can produce immunologically active substances, as well as some hormones. On the other hand, the immune cells themselves are accessible to the influence of hormones. Currently, the so-called cross-regulation of endocrine and immune mechanisms in the balance of pro- and anti-inflammatory responses has not been sufficiently studied. Among other autoimmune lesions, autoimmune thyropathies occupy a significant place. The development of autoimmune damage to the thyroid gland (TG) is a complex process, which is the result of the interaction of tissue-infiltrating lymphocytes and thyrocytes capable of expressing a wide range of molecules involved in the immune response. Immunological and immunogenetic factors play a major role in the pathogenesis of autoimmune thyroid diseases, such as autoimmune thyroiditis (AIT) and Graves' disease (GD). Despite the fact that more than 100 years have passed since the first description of AIT, and HD has been known for many centuries, the mechanisms of development of these pathologies have not yet been fully elucidated.*

Keywords: *thyroid gland, immune response, autoimmune thyropathies, T-regulatory cells, T-helper cells 17.*

ВКЛАД ЦЕНТРАЛЬНЫХ РЕГУЛЯТОРОВ ИММУННОГО ОТВЕТА В РАЗВИТИЕ ЗАБОЛЕВАНИЙ ЩИТОВИДНОЙ ЖЕЛЕЗЫ

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Аннотация. Специфические взаимоотношения эндокринной и иммунной систем представлены многочисленными факторами и механизмами, формирующими структуру и обеспечивающими функцию каждой из двух систем. Например, иммунокомпетентные клетки могут продуцировать иммунологически активные вещества, а также некоторые гормоны. С другой стороны, сами иммунные клетки доступны влиянию гормонов. В настоящее время недостаточно изучена так называемая перекрестная регуляция эндокринных и иммунных механизмов в балансе про- и противовоспалительных реакций. Среди других аутоиммунных поражений значительное место занимают аутоиммунные тиреопатии. Развитие аутоиммунного поражения щитовидной железы (ТГ) — сложный процесс, который является результатом взаимодействия тканевых лимфоцитов и тироцитов, способных экспрессировать широкий спектр молекул, участвующих в иммунном ответе. Иммунологические и иммуногенетические факторы играют важную роль в патогенезе аутоиммунных заболеваний щитовидной железы, таких как аутоиммунный тиреоидит (АИТ) и болезнь Грейвса (БГ). Несмотря на то, что со времени первого описания АИТ прошло более 100 лет, а БГ известна уже много столетий, механизмы развития этих патологий до сих пор полностью не выяснены.

Ключевые слова: щитовидная железа, иммунный ответ, аутоиммунные тиреопатии, Т-регуляторные клетки, Т-хелперы 17.

Introduction. According to the World Health Organization, cases of autoimmune diseases double every 5-10 years. Among the majority of endocrine glands subject to an autoimmune process, the thyroid gland (TG) is affected especially often. Autoimmune thyroid diseases account for 30% of all autoimmune pathologies, including two main clinical subtypes: Graves' disease (GD) and autoimmune thyroiditis (AIT) [1–5]. T regulatory cells (Treg, regulatory T lymphocytes, suppressor T cells) are central regulators of the immune response. Their main function is to control the strength and duration of a complex multicomponent immune reaction, immunosuppression through the synthesis of IL-10 and transforming growth factor beta (TGF- β). They inhibit the occurrence and development of autoimmune diseases, providing dominant immunological tolerance to self-antigens. TGF- β inhibits the formation of inflammatory CD4+ T helper cells (Th1, Th17) and suppresses the release of their main cytokines – IFN- γ and IL-17 [6, 7]. Peripheral autotolerance is maintained by CD25+ CD4+ Tregs, which actively suppress the activation and expansion of potentially pathogenic autoreactive T cells normally present in the immune system. When Tregs are reduced in number or impaired in function, their immunosuppressive function is reduced and thus lost, thereby effectively inhibiting excessive immune responses, which in turn leads to an increased risk of autoimmune diseases. CD4+ Tregs contain surface molecules: CD5, CD45RB, CD25, CD62L, CD38. Among them, the expression of CD25 is the most constant and provides the protective function of these cells in autoimmune diseases. Foxp3 protein is a key transcription factor that controls the development and function of Tregs and is expressed mainly in their nucleus [8, 9]. T helper 17 (Th17) cells are a recently discovered subset of CD4+ T cells primarily characterized by the production of interleukin (IL)-17A, IL-17F, IL-21, and IL-22. These cells and their cytokines play a key role in the development of various autoimmune diseases. According to a number of studies, Th17 cells and IL-17 are closely related to the incidence of AIT and HD. IL-1 β , IL-6 and IL-23, together with the expression of the transcription factor retinoid-related receptor gamma (ROR γ t) and activation of the signal converter and activator of intracellular transcription-3 (STAT3), are involved in the differentiation of Th17 cells. ROR γ t knockout animals exhibit a decrease in the number of Th17 cells and IL-17 expression and, as a consequence, a decrease in the incidence of autoimmune diseases [8–12]. Th17 is a key effector in the immune response and plays a critical role in autoimmunity and inflammation. In turn, Tregs control the overall immune response and maintain peripheral immune tolerance by regulating the activity of

effector T cells. One recent study found that microRNAs play an important role in regulating the pathogenesis of autoimmune diseases by changing the Th17/Treg ratio [13]. Disruption of Th17 and Treg cellular homeostasis plays an important role in the formation of autoimmunity and the development of inflammation. Quantitative and functional “imbalance” of Th17/Treg cells is one of the main links in the pathogenesis of many autoimmune diseases, such as HD, type I diabetes mellitus, systemic lupus erythematosus and rheumatoid arthritis, but its regulatory mechanisms are still poorly understood [2, 14–18]. T regulatory cells CD4+ T cells are divided into various subgroups, including Th1, Th2, Treg and Th17 lymphocytes. Tregs, originally termed “suppressor T cells” in 1970, are a heterogeneous population of lymphocytes characterized by immunosuppressive function. These cells regulate the protective immune response through direct cell-cell interactions or through cytokines such as TGF- β and IL-10 [19, 20]. To date, several subsets of human Treg cells have been identified, including CD4+ CD25+ Treg cells, CD4+ CD69+ Treg cells, IL10-producing regulatory type 1 (Tr1) cells, and CD8+ CD122+ Treg cells. A subset of Treg cells was first described as CD4+ cells expressing the carrier carrier Foxp3 and IL-2 (CD25). In humans, CD4+ CD25+ T cells constitute 5–10% of peripheral CD4+ T cells and are involved in the pathogenesis of a number of autoimmune diseases. Another subset of CD4+ Treg cells is represented by CD69 expression lacking Foxp3. These CD4+ CD69+ Treg cells mainly exert their suppressive activity through the synthesis of IL-10 and TGF- β [11, 12]. Tr1 was characterized by Roncarolo et al. This subset of Treg cells can suppress T cell and antigen presenting cell mediated immune responses, mainly through the secretion of IL-10 [14]. CD8+ CD122+ T cells are another type of Treg cell described by Suzuki et al. The suppressive function of these cells is carried out through the cytokine IL-10, but not through intercellular contact [23, 24]. Treg cells play an important role in the prevention of autoimmune reactions, have redox properties (balance of redox processes in the cell) compared to conventional CD4+ T helper cells and are more resistant to the pro-apoptotic effects of H₂O₂. This may be due to higher expression of thioredoxin (Txn1), which influences their effector role in preventing prolonged or excessive immune responses and possibly autoimmunity. Txn1 enzymatically reduces a variety of molecular substrates and is itself oxidized in the process. Regeneration of reduced Txn1 in the cytosol is carried out by selenoprotein thioredoxin reductase 1 (Txnrd1). The content of Txnrd1 in T cells and the expression of Treg cell markers are directly related to selenium consumption [2]. Treg cells play a major role in regulating autoimmunity, maintaining tissue homeostasis, microbial infection,

and tumor growth. In malignant tumors, these cells promote the progression of tumor growth by suppressing antitumor immunity. High tumor infiltration by Treg cells is associated with poor prognosis in various types of cancer [2, 6]. Autoimmune thyroid diseases and T-regulatory cells Many studies provide evidence of a close relationship between functional defects of Tregs or their absence and thyroid autoimmunity. In mouse models with a decrease in the number of CD4+CD25+ or CD8+CD122+ Tregs, the frequency and severity of AIT or GD increases, indicating a possible role of Treg deficiency in the development of autoimmune thyroid diseases. According to McLachlan et al., a decrease in CD4+CD25+ or CD8+CD122+ Tregs in genetically modified mice may cause a transition from HD to AIT, which may be associated with accompanying autoantibody responses to thyroglobulin and thyroid peroxidase. This discovery made it possible to determine the important role of Tregs in thyroid dysfunction in HD. It was also noted that prior transfer of CD4+CD25+ Tregs into CBA/J mice under experimental conditions can suppress AIT. The presented animal experiments highlight the crucial role of T-suppressors in suppressing autoimmune reactions in thyroid tissues. A number of clinical studies have revealed a decrease in the number or dysfunction of Tregs in patients with AIT or HD, which is consistent with data in animal models. Several studies have found an increase in the number of CD4+CD25hi or CD4+CD25+int-hiCD127+lo Tregs in adult patients with active GD and in children with AIT, while no significant deficit in the number of Tregs was detected. This discrepancy may be due to different detection markers for Treg cells. For example, Pan et al. chose CD4+CD25int-hiCD127lo as detection markers, whereas the study by Xue et al. CD4+CD25hi markers were used. Different age categories of onset and stage of the disease may also be associated with the number of Tregs [6].

Mechanisms of quantitative and functional defects of T cells in patients with autoimmune thyroid diseases

Under the influence of external triggers, an innate genetic predisposition can lead to the activation or suppression of autoreactive CD4+ T cells of the thyroid gland, including Th17 and Treg cells. Recently, Yan et al. reported that in Chinese patients with autoimmune thyroid diseases, the frequencies of the IL-17F/rs763780 and IL-17A/rs3819025 genotypes, which are associated with Th17 differentiation, were significantly different from controls. It has been suggested that the single nucleotide polymorphism (SNP) IL-17F/rs763780 may influence susceptibility to autoimmune thyroid diseases, and IL 17A/rs3819025 is likely a

protective factor for GD. In addition, IL-23R SNPs, including rs2201841, rs10889677 and rs7530511, have been shown to be associated with OH in Caucasian patients. These variants may predispose to OH by altering the expression and/or function of IL-23R, thereby promoting the Th17 differentiation process. Moreover, many studies have reported increased expression of IL-6 in HD and OH groups. IL-6, which is induced by IL-1 β , is particularly important because it shifts the balance of Th17 and Treg cells towards Th17.

Conclusion. The specific relationship between the endocrine and immune systems is irrefutable. Various studies have shown that Th17 and Treg deficiency and dysfunction are closely associated with thyroid autoimmunity and the severity of thyroid autoimmune diseases. The main mechanisms in this case are: genetic predisposition, certain biological molecules (eg, MB, SLAMF1), microelement status, and possibly the composition of the intestinal microbiota. T cells may be targeted in the development of new ways to maintain immunological tolerance to self-antigens. Taking into account the current research and creation of a large number of immunobiological drugs based on monoclonal antibodies to correct the imbalance of Th17 and Treg cells in various autoimmune diseases, attempts are being made to use some of them for autoimmune thyropathies. Further studies are needed to confirm the effectiveness of this therapy against autoimmune thyroid diseases.

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